

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: FATODU****FIRST NAME: OLAIYA****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 16%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2019 on Windows 11)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which of the following is not a reason why American English is currently the dominant influence on "world English"?
- The magnitude of higher education in America vs. the U.K.
 - The magnitude of the publishing industry in America.
 - The magnitude of global mass media and media technology influence.
 - The number of tertiary education institutions in the US is more than those in the UK, Canada, and Australia combined.¹**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 25.

2. Choose the option that best represents the presentation of number or numbers in academic writing at Euclid University.
- The distance from the students' faculty to the university library is 2 kilometres.
 - Out of the five Response Papers that I have submitted thus far, the course instructor commented that I should resubmit two.²**
 - 6 students submitted their Response Paper Two late.
 - I am currently in Period Six of the expected 7 Periods required of me to complete this course.
3. The followings describe academic research except:
- Answering a question by obtaining information.
 - Choosing a university to do doctoral studies.³**
 - A process of systematic inquiry to answer a question that not only the researcher but also others want to solve.
 - It invites readers to think critically about evidence and reasoning.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 47–48.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth edition. Chicago guides to writing, editing, and publishing (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 19.

4. In Turabian author-date style, quotations in academic writing can be described by all of the following except:

- Citing the exact words of an author, and quotation marks are used to capture what the author has said
- Quotations are cited in-text by writing the name of the author in parenthesis, the year, and the page number that the information came from
- Quotations that are two to three lines take no quotation marks and are indented like a separate little paragraph⁴**

Quotations are cited in-text by writing the name of the author, just before the parenthesis, and the year and the page number that the information came from are both written in the parenthesis.

5. Which of the following is not one of the five elements of a good research argument?

- Synthesis: What do you hope to achieve in the study?⁵**
- Claim: What do you want me to believe? What is your point?
- Reason: Why do you say that? Why should I agree?
- Evidence: How do you know? Can you back it up?

⁴ Turabian, 371–75.

⁵ Turabian, 58.

6. Like any serious endeavour, oral presentations require all of the following except:

- Planning.
- Organization of ideas.
- Interactions with the audience before the presentation.**⁶
- Practice bearing in mind the short time usually allotted for the presentation.

7. Which of the following does not constitute plagiarism?

- When you quote exact words from a source.
- When you paraphrase ideas that are associated with a specific source, even if you don't quote exact words from it.
- When you use any ideas, data, or methods attributable to any source you consulted.
- When you point readers to sources that are relevant to a particular portion of your argument but not quoted or paraphrased.**⁷

⁶ Turabian, 131.

⁷ Turabian, 140.

8. 'Exploring a phenomenon by studying a group of people or individual in their natural environment' best represents which of the following qualitative research approach
- Phenomenological approach
 - Ethnographic approach⁸**
 - Narrative approach
 - Grounded theory approach

⁸ Adu Philip, *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study*, YouTube Video, 2016, accessed September 25, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708>.

9. Which of the following best represents the sequence of chapters in a dissertation that is qualitative research?
- Introduction ► literature review ► methodology and research approach ► findings and interpretation ► analysis and synthesis of findings ► Conclusions and recommendations
 - Introduction ► literature review and research approach ► methodology ► findings ► analysis, interpretation, and synthesis of findings ► Conclusions and recommendations
 - Introduction ► literature review ► methodology and research approach ► findings ► analysis, interpretation, and synthesis of findings ► Conclusions and recommendations⁹**
 - Introduction and literature review ► methodology ► research approach ► findings ► analysis, interpretation, and synthesis of findings ► Conclusions and recommendations

⁹Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*, Fourth edition. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2019), 73–88.

10. According to Course ACA-401D at Euclid University, which of the following is True
- A good Ph.D. work is expected to have a properly formatted bibliography with 100-150 entries, of which less than 20% should be journal entries
 - A good Ph.D. work is expected to have a properly formatted bibliography with 250-300 entries, of which 20% or more should be journal entries
 - A good Ph.D. work is expected to have a properly formatted bibliography with 250-300 entries which must be 100% journal entries
 - A good Ph.D. work is expected to have a properly formatted bibliography with 100-150 entries, of which 20% or more should be journal entries¹⁰**

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2019.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

———. “Thesis/Dissertation Evaluation Form.” Euclid University, n.d.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition. Chicago guides to writing, editing, and publishing. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Adu, Philip. dir. *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study*. YouTube Video, 2016. Accessed September 25, 2022. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708>.

¹⁰ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, “Thesis/Dissertation Evaluation Form” (Euclid University, n.d.), 1.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.